

Supplementary Information (SI)

“Characterisation and assessment of two bio-based green aging methods for silver mock-up systems using multi-analytical techniques”

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S1 Method

S1.1 Aging methods

Fig. S 1: (a, b) aging chamber used for the EW method; (c-d): aging chamber used for the AS method.

S1.2 XRF measurements of reference silver objects

A handheld *Niton XL3t GOLDD+ XRF Analyzer* was used for the identification of the elemental compositions of silver coupons and reference objects, with the X-ray Ag tube at 200 mW, 50 kV, 40 μ A and 8 mm aperture. The measurement mode *General metal* was used, and spectra were acquired with the main range filter (6-19 keV), low range filter (3-6 keV) and light range filter (1-3 keV) sequentially. The pre-set measuring time was 30 seconds per filter. Helium purge was on for optimal detection of light elements during the measurements of reference silver objects. The *Thermo Scientific NDT* software was used for the data transfer and analysis.

XRF measurements of the reference objects were implemented on multiple positions on each object (Fig. S 2), with the measurement mode of General Metals and with helium purge on. Table S 1 presents the elements of interest for each measurement position on the reference objects.

Fig. S 2: XRF measurement positions on the reference objects.

Table S 1: XRF signal intensities of the reference objects. Only the elements of interest are presented.

Sample name	Measurement position	Measurement mode	Duration (s)	Ag (wt%)	Zn (wt%)	Cu (wt%)	Ni (wt%)	Fe (wt%)	Ti (wt%)	Si (wt%)
silver bracelet	sp1	General Metals	90.72	91.595	< LOD	6.852	< LOD	0.077	0.041	0.105
silver necklace pendant	sp1	General Metals	90.04	90.747	1.409	3.839	< LOD	< LOD	0.064	2.386
silver necklace pendant	sp2	General Metals	90.64	90.784	1.421	3.926	< LOD	0.088	0.059	2.381
silver necklace pendant	sp3	General Metals	90.88	88.403	2.162	4.707	< LOD	< LOD	0.047	3.179
silver-plated teaspoon1	sp1	General Metals	90.12	98.320	0.040	0.062	< LOD	< LOD	0.048	0.373
silver-plated teaspoon1	sp2	General Metals	91.28	98.359			< LOD	< LOD	0.076	0.311
silver-plated teaspoon2	sp3	General Metals	90.38	98.406	0.031	0.059	0.074	0.094	0.038	0.264
silver-plated teaspoon2	sp4	General Metals	90.27	98.611	< LOD	0.047	< LOD	< LOD	0.042	0.226
silver card case	sp1	General Metals	90.63	94.915	< LOD	0.726	< LOD	0.098	0.107	< LOD
silver card case	sp2	General Metals	91.27	96.400		1.140	< LOD	0.114	0.085	0.251
silver card case	sp3	General Metals	90.96	85.250	< LOD	5.145	< LOD	< LOD	0.097	< LOD
silver card case	sp4	General Metals	91.37	95.570		2.087	< LOD	< LOD	0.052	0.326
silver card case	sp5	General Metals	91.51	94.835		2.338	< LOD	0.127	0.098	0.617
silver card case	sp6	General Metals	91.32	89.507	< LOD	5.183	< LOD	< LOD	0.096	< LOD
silver plated tea filter	sp1	General Metals	91.20	85.073			1.496	0.902	0.451	< LOD
silver plated tea filter	sp2	General Metals	91.15	76.701			3.168	0.804	0.391	< LOD
silver plated tea filter	sp3	General Metals	91.25	77.267			2.850	0.866	0.415	< LOD

silver plated tea filter	sp4	General Metals	91.27	63.404			6.504	0.254	0.038	< LOD
silver plated tea filter	sp5	General Metals	90.35	93.857			0.176	0.119	0.058	< LOD
silver plated tea filter	sp6	General Metals	90.99	94.277			0.175	< LOD	0.092	< LOD
silver plated tea filter	sp7	General Metals	22.06	85.621			2.103	0.142	< LOD	
silver plated tea filter	sp8	General Metals	95.72	94.576	0.929	2.218	0.378	0.168	0.097	0.275
silver plated tea filter	sp9	General Metals	91.19	58.009			7.783	0.762	< LOD	< LOD
silver plated tea filter	sp10	General Metals	95.39	85.742	< LOD	8.598	1.874	0.088	0.174	< LOD
silver plated tea filter	sp11	General Metals	94.27	58.574	< LOD	25.452	9.253	0.119	< LOD	< LOD

S1.3 Cluster spectra based on PCA analysis of Raman map data

Fig. S 3: PCA analysis-derived cluster maps and spectra of (a) SS1-04 and (b) SS1-05. The colours for the image pixels represent the spatial locations of the spectra of the corresponding colour (and have no further meanings).

S2 characterisation

S2.1 Optical microscopy observations

Fig. S 4 presents the optical microscopy – bright field (OM-BF) images of 12 SS2 and 12 SP2 coupons aged in the aging batch S2-EW1 and S2-AS1. The S2-001, -002, -003, -004, -005 and -006 coupons were aged with 2 eggs for 10, 30, 60, 90, 150 and 240 min respectively, while the S2-007, -008, -009, -010, -011 and -012 coupons were aged with 400 ml 20% albumin solution for 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 h respectively. The colours of the coupons indicate that the aging rate of the albumin solution is much slower than that of the boiled egg white method. On both SS2 and SP2 coupons aged with AS for 6 h (-011) and 7 h (-012), a ring-structure is visible. Images of higher magnifications for the ring structure can be seen in the SEM-EDX images in the main text of the article.

Fig. S 4: OM-BF images of the artificially aged SS2 (001-012) and SP2 (001-012) coupons. Magnification: 10x.

S2.2 Raman spectroscopy measurements

S2.2.1 Experimental conditions and reference spectra

The experimental conditions established for the SS1 coupons included: 1) 50x objective, 532 nm excitation wavelength, laser power of 0.3-0.4 mW, exposure time of 3-5 seconds, 30-40 accumulations; 2) 50x objective, 785 nm excitation, laser power of 3 mW, exposure time of 5-10 seconds, 2-10 accumulations. Different from the SS1 coupons, the SP1 coupons (Ag999) exhibited significant heating effects and therefore were excluded from further measurements.

Fig. S 5 presents Raman spectra of the reference powder samples collected under the excitations of 532 nm (a) and 785 nm (b). Because of strong heating effects caused by the laser radiation, the spectra of acanthite cannot be collected and were thus excluded from the figure. Further, under the excitation of 785 nm, no clear characteristic bands were obtained for cuprite and chalcocite, which were thus not included in Fig. S 5b.

Fig. S 5: Raman single-point spectra of a) the reference powder samples under the excitation of 532 nm; b) reference powder samples under the excitation of 785 nm (no signal for cuprite Cu_2O and chalcocite Cu_2S).

Fig. S 6 shows the single-point spectra collected on chalcocite reference powder. It is observed that the chalcocite sample was very sensitive to the experimental settings. For example, with 0.3 mW laser power, 5 seconds exposure time and 20 accumulations, it has transformed to cuprite with clear heating effects, while with a 0.5 mW laser power, 4s exposure time and 40 accumulations, a transformation occurred in the direction to covellite. Using a laser power of 0.3 mW and exposure time below 5 seconds, the spectra of chalcocite showed a broad band centred at 296-3068 cm^{-1} , which is compatible with some literature indicating Cu-S stretching modes at 300 cm^{-1} .

Fig. S 6: Raman single-point spectra of the reference powder sample Cu_2S with different experimental conditions.

Fig. S 7: Raman measurement spots on the silver reference objects.

Fig. S 8: Raman single-point spectra of the reference objects together with the micro-images before and after measurement for each measurement point: a) necklace pendant; b) tea-filter; c) card-case; d) silver-plated brass spoon; e) measurement positions sp1 and sp2 on the bracelet; e-2) sp3 on the bracelet; e-4) sp4 on the bracelet.

S2.2.2 Measurements of SS2 coupons

Fig. S 9: Raman map spectra of the AS aged SS2-024 coupon at exposure times of 5h and 10h.

S2.3 LSV measurements on tarnished coupons

LSV measurements were performed on two mirror-like SS1 coupons, i.e., SS1-04 and SS1-05, using *PLECO* electronic pencil. The reduction curves of in the LSV plots of these two coupons confirmed the presence of Ag_2S and Cu_2S . Meanwhile, Ag_2S is observed to be further developed on the EW aged SS1-04, while the reduction curve of Cu_2S is clearer on the AS aged SS1-05. On both coupons, some copper oxides were also detected, although their reduction curves are not obvious in the LSV plots. Due to the accumulation of metallic copper on the coupon surface during the electrochemical reduction process by LSV, which led to an unpleasant red-brown colour, the LSV measurement was not continued for other coupons.

Fig. S 10: LSV plots of SS1-04 (red plot) SS1-05 (blue plot).

S2.4 XRD measurements

XRD measurement was also performed on the pure silver coupon SP2-024*, which was aged with AS for 10 h. Acanthite (Ag_2S) was clearly identified (Fig. S 11).

Fig. S 11: XRD measurements of SP2-024*: (a) overview of the spectrum; (b) higher-scale view of the spectrum.

S2.5 SEM-EDX measurements

Fig. S 12: SEM-EDX mapping on SS2-012: a) SEM-BSE image of an observation site; b) map spectrum; c) EDX elemental maps of Cu, Ag, O and S.

Fig. S 13: SEM_EDX mapping of an observation site on (a) the unpolished side of SS3_02 after aging and (b) the polished side of SS3_02 after aging. Magnification: 3,000x. Scale bar: 5 μ m.

In order to obtain more details about the tarnish composition of S3 coupons, EDX spectrum analysis was further performed on the same areas on SS3-02 before and after aging, but with a larger observation view (Fig. S 14). It is observed that after aging the atomic ratios of Cu for both sides significantly increase with similar magnitudes, while those of Ag decrease. While it makes sense that the S atomic ratios for both sides increase after aging, since the H_2S vapour was used to tarnish the coupon, it is interesting to observe that the O atomic ratio slightly decreases for the unpolished side (from ca. 5% to 2%) and there is no obvious change on the polished side. Such observations indicate that sulphidation was dominant in the tarnishing process of this coupon and thus sulphides should be the main product rather than oxides. The increase of S atomic ratio for the polished side (ca. 12%) is more obvious than that for the unpolished side (ca. 8%), indicating that the surface polishing can result in a higher sulphidation rate and a more tarnished state.

Fig. S 14: SEM-EDX analysis of (a) the unpolished side and (b) polished side of SS3-02 before and after aging . Magnification: 500x. Scale bar: 50 µm.

S2.6 AFM/KPFM measurements

Fig. S 15: OM image of the island structure on the surface of SS1-05. Magnification: 50x. Scale bar: 25 µm.

Table S 2: Overview of the coupons investigated with AFM / KPFM.

Coupon no.	Sample series	Surface finishing	Aging test no.	Aging method	Exposure time	Surface structure through OM	AFM height (object)	KPFM (work function difference)
SP1-02	S1	Mirror-like	S1-AT1	AS (200 ml)	5 h	No islands or rings	40 nm	0.05 eV
SP1-03	S1	Mirror-like	S1-AT1	EW (4 eggs)	30 min	No islands or rings	70 nm	0.04 eV
SS1-05	S1	Mirror-like	S1-AT1	AS (200 ml)	5 h	Various sized beige islands on light blue substrate	40 nm	0.02 eV
SP2-006	S2	Semi-polished	S2-AT1	EW (2 egg)	240 min	No islands or rings	230 nm	0.05 eV
SP2-011	S2	Semi-polished	S2-AT1	AS (400 ml)	6 h	Rings	95 nm	0.02 eV
SP2-012	S2	Semi-polished	S2-AT1	AS (400 ml)	7 h	Rings	200 nm	0.1- 0.2 eV
SS2-006	S2	Semi-polished	S2-AT1	EW (2 egg)	240 min	No islands or rings	150 nm	0.09 eV
SS2-011	S2	Semi-polished	S2-AT1	AS (400ml)	6 h	Rings	150 nm	0.05 eV
SS2-012	S2	Semi-polished	S2-AT1	AS (400 ml)	7 h	Rings	130 nm	0.05 eV
SS3-test1	S3	Unpolished	S2.AT1 (together with the S2 coupons)	AS (400 ml)	7 h	Rings	110 - 220 nm	0.04 - 0.14 eV

Fig. S 16: AFM (upper row) and KPFM (lower row) micrographs of (a-b) SP1-02 and (c-d) SP1-03 coupons.

Fig. S 17: AFM micrograph of the SS2-012 coupon larger surface area demonstrating ring-structure.

Fig. S 18: AFM (upper row) and KPFM (lower row) micrographs of (a-b) SP2-006, (c-d) SP2-011 and (e-f) SP2-012 coupons.